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Artificial Intelligence and the Speed Asymmetry

Understanding the Governance Challenges Created by the Diverging Speeds of AI, Markets and Public Institutions

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KEY MESSAGES

- Artificial intelligence is simultaneously transforming nearly every economic and social sector at a speed without historical precedent.
- Markets adopt AI out of competitive necessity, without waiting for societies to adapt.
- Governments operate with tools designed for a world that changed over decades, yet AI is reshaping entire sectors within years.
- The transformation of work unfolds on three layers: substitution, reconfiguration, and creation. Substitution yields immediate but non-differentiating gains; durable competitive advantage lies in the second and third.
- This speed asymmetry is a defining political challenge of our era: its consequences will be local even though the technology is global.
- Southeast Asia is especially exposed: a near-US\$1-trillion AI opportunity by 2030 sits alongside uneven adoption, automatable export-sector jobs, lagging skills, and still-voluntary ASEAN governance.

1. A REVOLUTION OF UNPRECEDENTED SCOPE, SPEED, AND COGNITIVE REACH

Artificial intelligence is not just another technology, but the nature of its novelty must be stated precisely. It is not unprecedented in every respect: like earlier waves, it automates tasks, raises productivity, and displaces some work. What sets it apart is a combination of three features: the breadth of its reach (it touches nearly every sector at once), the pace at which it spreads, and, most distinctively, the kind of work it automates. For the first time, a general-purpose technology operates directly on cognitive tasks rather than only physical or routine ones. Public sentiment already registers the shift: international surveys compiled by Stanford's AI Index find populations worldwide expecting AI to reshape daily life within a few years (Stanford HAI, 2024).

The speed of diffusion is the clearest break with the past. ChatGPT reached one million users within five days of launch (Altman, 2022) and an estimated one hundred million monthly users two months later (Hu, 2023, citing UBS). Organisational adoption has followed the same curve: 88% of organisations worldwide reported using AI in at least one function, up from 78% a year earlier and 55% two years before that (McKinsey & Company, 2025).

The cognitive character of the technology is what makes it more than a faster machine: it extends and simulates human cognitive functions such as memory, attention, language, inference and creativity, blurring the boundary between the human and the machine (Floridi, 2014; Ismayilzada et al., 2024). Even its designers cannot fully explain how its underlying computations give rise to behaviour resembling reasoning, metaphor, and creativity (Sorin & Klang, 2023; Lipton, 2018). In this sense AI functions less like a conventional tool than like a cognitive collaborator (Seeber et al., 2020; Łukasik & Gut, 2025), a shift some have argued is significant enough to mark a distinct epoch (Andrès, 2025).

Yet alongside the well-known concerns about the technology itself, this transformation raises a challenge that is easy to overlook. It is a structural mismatch of tempo: AI advances on a timescale of months, markets adapt on a timescale of quarters and years, and societies and institutions can change only on a timescale of years and decades. This **speed asymmetry**, rather than the capabilities of AI as such, is the central argument of this brief. What follows shows how fast and how deeply the transformation already runs, and why the mismatch of speeds it creates is a challenge of its own.

2. THE PACE OF CHANGE: MEASURABLE IMPACT ACROSS ALL SECTORS

The first term of the asymmetry is the sheer speed and breadth of AI's advance. The transformations it drives are not prospective: they are already underway, documented, and quantified across every economic sector: the evidence that the first of our three forces is moving fast.

Industry and Manufacturing

AI-driven adaptive robotics and computer-vision quality inspection are now in series production at manufacturers such as Fanuc and BMW, enabling new levels of flexibility and defect detection. Firms rarely publish comparable, independently audited performance figures, and the most significant measurable gains in manufacturing so far come from AI-enabled logistics and supply-chain optimisation rather than from production itself.

Logistics and Supply Chains

AI turns static planning into self-adapting forecasting. Migros (Türkiye) cut inventory days by more than 11% while raising on-shelf availability, using AI-driven replenishment across 2,000 stores (Invent Analytics, 2022). Across industries, McKinsey's analysis of AI-enabled distribution finds reductions of 20–30% in inventory, 5–20% in logistics costs, and 5–15% in procurement spend (McKinsey & Company, 2024).

Healthcare and Drug Discovery

In medical imaging, a large UK–US evaluation of an AI breast-cancer screening system showed an absolute reduction of 9.4% (US) and 2.7% (UK) in false negatives, alongside fewer false positives (McKinney et al., 2020). In structural biology, DeepMind's AlphaFold used deep-learning neural networks to predict the three-dimensional structure of virtually all known proteins (approximately 200 million), reaching accuracy levels not anticipated for another decade, and removing a longstanding bottleneck in drug development (Jumper et al., 2021). In drug discovery itself, Insilico Medicine used generative AI to identify a novel target and design a candidate molecule for idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis in roughly 18 months (compared with the 2.5–4 years typical of conventional approaches), and the resulting drug has shown positive preliminary results in a Phase 2a randomised controlled trial (Ren et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2025).

Education and Knowledge Work

In knowledge work, a randomized field experiment with BCG consultants found that those using GPT-4 on tasks within its capabilities completed 12% more tasks, 25% faster, and at 40% higher quality, but performance fell on tasks outside the model's reliable frontier (Dell'Acqua et al., 2023). In a field study of more than 5,000 customer-support agents, an AI assistant raised productivity by 14% on average and by 34% for novices, with little effect on experts (Brynjolfsson, Li & Raymond, 2023). In education, adaptive courseware has a longer evidence base: Carnegie Mellon's Open Learning Initiative statistics course let students reach equivalent mastery in about half the time, and an independent multi-institution trial found students completed it 25% faster (Lovett et al., 2008; Bowen et al., 2014). Khan Academy's platform is associated with roughly 20% greater-than-expected learning gains (up to ~30% for students furthest behind) (Khan Academy, 2024); evidence specific to its Khanmigo AI tutor is still mixed and emerging.

Marketing and Customer Experience

In customer-facing functions, conversational AI increasingly handles routine interactions at scale. KLM reported that its AI assistant, built with DigitalGenius, supports more than 50% of customer inquiries, freeing agents for complex cases (KLM / DigitalGenius). Retailers widely report higher conversion and lower returns from AI personalisation and virtual try-on tools, though published vendor figures vary too much to cite a single reliable number.

These data converge on a single finding: AI does not incrementally improve existing processes; it structurally reconstitutes them.

3. THREE STRATEGIC LAYERS OF WORK TRANSFORMATION

If the sectoral data show how fast AI advances, the transformation of work shows how deeply that advance cuts, and where human adaptation begins to lag behind it. What we are experiencing today is not only a technological shift: it is a profound redefinition of human work and value creation. AI is transforming the world of work on three distinct strategic layers, each with implications for competitiveness, education, governance, and economic models (Autor, 2015; Wilson & Daugherty, 2018; WEF, 2025).

Substitution: The Efficiency Layer

The first transformation is the most visible, but the least strategic: it delivers real gains that every competitor eventually captures, so it confers no lasting edge. AI substitutes tasks that are routine, repetitive, and standardised, generating significant productivity gains while raising legitimate concerns about employment in exposed sectors (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2022; McKinsey Global Institute, 2023). Yet substitution is merely the entry point. Every past technological wave (from mechanisation to computerisation) produced substitution (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). What matters for decision-makers is what comes after.

Reconfiguration: The Transformation Layer

The deeper shift is here. AI does not eliminate most jobs: it transforms them from within (Autor, 2015; Wilson & Daugherty, 2018). Across all sectors, work is being reorganised around four forces: *collaboration* (humans and AI reasoning together), *creativity* (exploring and prototyping at unprecedented speed), *reasoning* (strategic, ethical, and contextual judgment that only humans bring), and *orchestration* (managing intelligent

systems, coordinating agents, steering cognitive workflows) (Mollick & Mollick, 2023; Wilson & Daugherty, 2018). Tomorrow's competitiveness will not come from replacing people, but from elevating them into hybrid roles where human and artificial intelligence genuinely complement each other. This is where nations, universities, and companies will differentiate themselves.

Creation: The Strategic Frontier

AI is generating entirely new professions, structures, and ecosystems: AI-native jobs that did not exist three years ago, hybrid intelligence teams combining humans and autonomous agents, and emergent roles in governance, ethics, supervision, model evaluation, and data ecosystems (WEF, 2025; Dafoe, 2018). New socio-technical architectures are redefining how value is created: what some analysts call the birth of a new cognitive economy (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2022). The organisations and nations that master these new ecosystems will lead the next decade. Those that remain focused solely on substitution will fall behind.

This three-layer framework has a direct policy implication: most current education and training systems are calibrated for the substitution layer (OECD, 2023). Building capacity in reconfiguration and creation is the urgent task for governments and universities alike.

4. THE SPEED ASYMMETRY: THE CORE POLITICAL CHALLENGE

We can now state the core problem directly. The transformations documented in Sections 2 and 3 are not, in themselves, the primary challenge for policymakers: they are evidence of how fast and how deep the first force runs. As argued at the outset, a decisive challenge, and the one this brief foregrounds, is the structural asymmetry between three forces that change at radically different tempos: what the technology governance literature calls the “pacing problem” (Thierer, 2016; Dafoe, 2018).

Force	Tempo of change	Dynamics
Artificial Intelligence	Months	Capability advances with each model generation. For the first time, skilled cognitive tasks, not just manual ones, are becoming automatable (WEF, 2025).
Markets	Quarters to years	Firms adopt AI out of economic survival, not curiosity. Once a competitor gains a decisive cost or speed advantage through automation, rivals must match it, or lose the market.
Societies and Governments	Years to decades	Education systems, legal frameworks, and social protection were built for a world that changed over decades. They cannot be rewritten at the speed AI reshapes the sectors they govern.

It is in the gap between these three tempos that the true risk of the AI transition lies: rapid cognitive automation whose benefits concentrate among a small number of actors, while a significant share of the workforce sees its jobs transformed or displaced faster than it can adapt (McKinsey Global Institute, 2023; OECD, 2023).

This observation applies to all advanced economies. It takes on particular urgency in Southeast Asia, where rapid economic growth, young working populations, and high dependence on sectors with significant automatable task content (manufacturing, logistics, services) amplify both the opportunities and the vulnerabilities.

5. WHY SOUTHEAST ASIA IS ESPECIALLY EXPOSED

Nowhere is the speed asymmetry sharper than in Southeast Asia, because the region combines a very fast adoption ceiling with unusually slow institutional and social shock-absorbers. The opportunity is real: AI could add close to US\$1 trillion to ASEAN's GDP by 2030 (a 13–18% uplift) in a region of 680 million people, more than 60% of them under 35 (Kearney, 2020; ASEAN AMMSTI, 2024). But that headline masks four region-specific vulnerabilities that turn the global asymmetry into an acute regional risk.

Adoption is real but profoundly uneven. Singapore sits among the world's highest rates of AI diffusion, while much of the region trails by an estimated two to three years. The gap is starkest in investment: historically Southeast Asia attracted roughly US\$2 per capita in AI investment, against US\$68 in Singapore and US\$155 in the United States (Kearney, 2020). The result is a two-speed ASEAN, in which the asymmetry hits hardest precisely where adaptive capacity is weakest.

Employment is concentrated in automatable, trade-exposed work. Manufacturing and electronics assembly, logistics, and business-process outsourcing (call centres and back-office data work) are core regional employers and among the most exposed to substitution. Large informal sectors compound the risk: many workers sit outside the social-protection systems that would normally cushion a transition, so displacement translates directly into lost livelihoods rather than managed reallocation (WEF, 2025).

Skills systems are not keeping pace. Roughly 40% of jobs in emerging-market economies (the category covering most of Southeast Asia) are exposed to AI, against about 60% in advanced economies (IMF, 2024). Demand for AI skills is already becoming a hiring filter: in a global survey, two-thirds of leaders said they would not hire a candidate lacking AI skills (Microsoft & LinkedIn, 2024). Yet regional curricula and training systems are not closing that gap fast enough: the human-tempo term of the asymmetry made concrete.

Governance is deliberately soft, and binding rules lag adoption. ASEAN's approach is principles-based and voluntary: the ASEAN Guide on AI Governance and Ethics (February 2024) is explicitly non-binding, supplemented by an Expanded Gen AI Guide (January 2025) and a Responsible AI Roadmap 2025–2030 (ASEAN, 2024; ASEAN, 2025). Legally binding regional interoperability is expected only with the Digital Economy Framework Agreement (DEFA, anticipated around end-2026), while national AI laws in Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia and Malaysia are only now converging. Dependence on a handful of North American and Chinese platforms adds a digital-sovereignty dimension to the gap.

These vulnerabilities are not fatalities: they are precisely where coordinated policy can compress the asymmetry. They define the priority axes of action below.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICYMAKERS

The challenge posed by the speed asymmetry cannot be resolved through sectoral adjustments alone. It requires a strategic, coordinated response between governments, academic institutions, and economic actors: precisely what the Policy Trialogue format embodies.

1	Anticipate, do not react. Establish dedicated foresight units focused on AI's impact on employment and qualifications, with 3-, 5-, and 10-year horizons. Identify sector by sector the transitions that must be supported before they generate social ruptures.
2	Reform education systems in depth. Shift from transmitting fixed knowledge to building durable competencies: critical thinking, complex problem-solving, human-AI collaboration, and digital ethics. Calibrate specifically for reconfiguration and creation layers, not only substitution.
3	Redistribute productivity gains. AI-driven productivity increases do not redistribute themselves spontaneously. Fiscal mechanisms, professional transition funds, and value-sharing arrangements must be designed ex ante, not in response to a crisis.
4	Build regional alliances. No mid-sized country can exert meaningful leverage alone against major technology powers. Common governance frameworks, on data, AI standards, credential interoperability, and ethical norms, constitute a lever of collective digital sovereignty for ASEAN.
5	Decide what must remain human. Certain domains, such as justice, critical healthcare, foundational education, and democratic decision-making, require human presence and accountability that cannot be delegated to automated systems. These boundaries must be set politically, not by default.
6	Institutionalise the tripartite dialogue. The government–industry–academia format illustrated by this Policy Trialogue is not a one-off event: it is the governance model best suited to the speed of transformation. Making it permanent and deriving binding recommendations from it is itself a recommendation.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence is transforming the world at a speed that our institutions are not yet equipped to absorb. This lag is not inevitable: it is the product of political choices, or the absence of them.

Societies cannot slow the technology. They can, however, protect their populations, anticipate transitions, redistribute gains, build alliances, and define the limits of what must not be automated.

The challenge this brief has traced is not artificial intelligence alone, but above all the structural speed asymmetry between the tempo of technological change, market adaptation, and institutional response.

In a world where cognition is multiplied by machines, what role do we want human beings to play?

This question can no longer be postponed. And answering it requires precisely the kind of cooperation that this Policy Trialogue seeks to build.

REFERENCES

A. Academic Articles and Books

- Acemoglu, D. & Restrepo, P. (2022). Tasks, Automation, and the Rise in US Wage Inequality. *Econometrica*, 90(5), 1973–2016.
- Altman, S. (2022). Public statement on ChatGPT surpassing one million users. *X (formerly Twitter)*, 5 December 2022.
- Andrès, L. (2025). The Nooacene: Defining and Naming the Epoch of Artificial Intelligence across Cultures and Languages. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17575357>
- Autor, D.H. (2015). Why Are There Still So Many Jobs? The History and Future of Workplace Automation. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 29(3), 3–30.
- Bowen, W.G., Chingos, M.M., Lack, K.A. & Nygren, T.I. (2014). Interactive Learning Online at Public Universities: Evidence from a Six-Campus Randomized Trial (ITHAKA S+R). *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 33(1), 94–111.
- Brynjolfsson, E. & McAfee, A. (2014). *The Second Machine Age: Work, Progress, and Prosperity in a Time of Brilliant Technologies*. W.W. Norton & Company, New York.
- Brynjolfsson, E., Li, D. & Raymond, L.R. (2023). Generative AI at Work. *NBER Working Paper*, No. 31161. National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Dafoe, A. (2018). AI Governance: A Research Agenda. *Future of Humanity Institute, University of Oxford*.
- Dell'Acqua, F., McFowland III, E., Mollick, E.R. et al. (2023). Navigating the Jagged Technological Frontier: Field Experimental Evidence of the Effects of AI on Knowledge Worker Productivity and Quality. *Harvard Business School Working Paper*, No. 24-013.
- Floridi, L. (2014). *The Fourth Revolution: How the Infosphere Is Reshaping Human Reality*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Hu, K. (2023). ChatGPT Sets Record for Fastest-Growing User Base: Analyst Note. *Reuters*, 2 February 2023 (citing UBS and Similarweb data).
- Ismayilzada, E., Paul, D., Bosselut, A. & van der Plas, L. (2024). Creativity in AI: Progresses and Challenges. *arXiv:2410.17218*.
- Jumper, J., Evans, R., Pritzel, A. et al. (2021). Highly Accurate Protein Structure Prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature*, 596, 583–589. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2> (Nobel Prize in Chemistry 2024).
- Lipton, Z.C. (2018). The Mythos of Model Interpretability. *Communications of the ACM*, 61(10), 36–43. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3233231>
- Lovett, M., Meyer, O. & Thille, C. (2008). The Open Learning Initiative: Measuring the Effectiveness of the OLI Statistics Course in Accelerating Student Learning. *Journal of Interactive Media in Education*, 2008(1).
- Łukasik, A. & Gut, A. (2025). From Robots to Chatbots: Unveiling the Dynamics of Human–AI Interaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, 1569277. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1569277>
- McKinney, S.M., Sieniek, M., Godbole, V. et al. (2020). International Evaluation of an AI System for Breast Cancer Screening. *Nature*, 577, 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1799-6>
- Mollick, E. & Mollick, L. (2023). Assigning AI: Seven Approaches for Students, with Prompts. *The Wharton School, University of Pennsylvania*.
- Ren, F., Ding, X., Zheng, M. et al. (2024). AlphaFold Accelerates Artificial Intelligence Powered Drug Discovery: Efficient Discovery of a Novel CDK20 Small Molecule Inhibitor. *Chemical Science*, 14, 1443–1452. (Also: Ren et al., *Nature Biotechnology*, 2024: generative AI discovery of TNIK inhibitor for IPF.)
- Seeber, I., Waizenegger, L., Seidel, S., Morana, S., Benbasat, I. & Leimeister, J.M. (2020). Machines as Teammates: A Research Agenda. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 35(6), 845–866. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-019-09627-0>
- Sorin, V. & Klang, E. (2023). Large Language Models and the Emergence Phenomena. *European Journal of Radiology Open*, 10, 100494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejro.2023.100494>
- Thierer, A. (2016). *Permissionless Innovation: The Continuing Case for Comprehensive Technological Freedom*. Mercatus Center, George Mason University.

Wilson, H.J. & Daugherty, P.R. (2018). Collaborative Intelligence: Humans and AI Are Joining Forces. *Harvard Business Review*, July–August 2018.

Xu, Z., Ren, F., Wang, P. et al. (2025). A Generative AI-Discovered TNIK Inhibitor for Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis: A Randomized Phase 2a Trial. *Nature Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-025-03743-2> (First proof-of-concept clinical validation of AI-driven drug discovery; ~18 months to preclinical candidate vs 2.5–4 years conventionally.)

B. Institutional Reports

ASEAN (2024). ASEAN Guide on AI Governance and Ethics. *ASEAN Secretariat, Jakarta* (voluntary, non-binding; adopted February 2024). The GDP-uplift estimate was endorsed in the ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Science, Technology and Innovation (AMMSTI) statement, June 2024.

ASEAN (2025). Expanded ASEAN Guide on AI Governance and Ethics: Generative AI; and ASEAN Responsible AI Roadmap 2025–2030. *ASEAN Secretariat, Jakarta*.

International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2024). Gen-AI: Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Work. *IMF Staff Discussion Note SDN/2024/001*, Washington, D.C. (source of the AI job-exposure figures: ~40% globally, ~60% in advanced economies, ~40% in emerging markets).

Kearney (2020). Racing Toward the Future: Artificial Intelligence in Southeast Asia. *Kearney* (source of the US\$1 trillion / 13–18% ASEAN GDP-uplift estimate by 2030 and the per-capita AI investment comparison).

Khan Academy (2024). Khan Academy Efficacy Results (2022–23 study of ~350,000 students). *Khan Academy* (~20% greater-than-expected learning gains for students reaching recommended usage; up to ~30% for those furthest behind). Evidence specific to the Khanmigo AI tutor remains preliminary.

McKinsey & Company (2023). The Economic Potential of Generative AI: The Next Productivity Frontier. *McKinsey Global Institute*.

McKinsey & Company (2024). AI in Supply-Chain and Distribution Operations. *McKinsey & Company*: reported reductions of 20–30% in inventory, 5–20% in logistics costs, and 5–15% in procurement spend for AI-enabled distribution operations.

McKinsey & Company (2025). The State of AI: How Organizations are Rewiring to Capture Value. *McKinsey Global Institute*.

Microsoft & LinkedIn (2024). 2024 Work Trend Index Annual Report: AI at Work Is Here. Now Comes the Hard Part. *Microsoft & LinkedIn* (global survey of 31,000 respondents across 31 countries; source of the 66% hiring-filter figure, which is global, not regional).

OECD (2023). OECD Employment Outlook 2023: Artificial Intelligence and the Labour Market. *Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Paris*.

Stanford University, Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence (HAI) (2024). Artificial Intelligence Index Report 2024. *Stanford HAI*.

World Economic Forum (WEF) (2020). The Future of Jobs Report 2020. *World Economic Forum, Geneva* (source of the 85-million-jobs-by-2025 estimate).

World Economic Forum (WEF) (2025). The Future of Jobs Report 2025. *World Economic Forum, Geneva*.

C. Company Case Studies

Invent Analytics (2022). Migros Case Study: Reducing Inventory Days and Increasing Availability. *Invent Analytics / invent.ai* (Migros Ticaret, Türkiye: inventory days reduced by more than 11%, availability +1.7%).

KLM / DigitalGenius (2019). AI-Assisted Customer Service at KLM Royal Dutch Airlines. *KLM and DigitalGenius* (AI supports more than 50% of customer inquiries).

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